

Manifattura Tabacchi Firenze, photo credits Giovanni Savi

**TOWARDS
INNOVATIVE,
INCLUSIVE AND
CREATIVE HUBS
IN EUROPEAN CITIES
A POLICY REPORT
BY CENTRINNO,
HUB-IN AND T-FACTOR
CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES**

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CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES

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1 - Introduction

Over the past decades, abandonment and decay of urban, industrial and rural heritage has occurred in many historic urban areas and cultural landscapes due to reduction of economic activities and closing down of industries. This has led to unemployment, disengagement and economic stagnation, contributing to breaking up traditional social structures, gentrification and over-reliance on volatile sectors, such as tourism.

Thanks to their symbolic and cultural value, and to their specific urban fabric, historic areas have the potential to be transformed into hubs of entrepreneurship, creativity, innovation, and social and cultural integration reaping the opportunities offered by, for instance, emerging creative sectors, digital technologies, the sharing and 'maker' economy, and social innovation. An evidence-based leveraging of historic and cultural assets' value can transform challenges into economic, social and cultural opportunities, while fully respecting the identity of the historic urban areas and cultural landscapes.

The innovation projects

CENTRINNO¹, **T-FACTOR**², and **HUB-IN**³ are the three so-called "Sister Projects" (SPs) funded under the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 from the 2019 call topic on "Transforming historic urban areas and/or cultural landscapes into hubs of entrepreneurship and social and cultural integration". The topic aimed at leveraging European cooperation to co-develop new approaches to the regeneration of cities and regions through the deployment of innovative solutions, particularly by linking innovative entrepreneurship, social integration and the reuse of historical heritage.

By collaborating as Sister Projects, CENTRINNO, T-Factor, and HUB-IN, involved a total of 26 European cities (+ 20 follower cities), 23 pilot areas, and 69 partners across the quadruple helix (local authorities, research and academia, SMEs and local businesses, CSOs and NGOs), activating several local ecosystems. This has represented a unique opportunity to experiment and scale up transformative regeneration processes in an age of uncertainty and disruptive changes across a diversity of geographies, cultures, socio-cultural capitals, and connotations of heritage that make European cities unique.

The similarities in overarching challenges and opportunities opened up valuable opportunities for the development of synergies across the three SPs that were explored in a series of joint Clustering Activities.

Working creatively and collaboratively across themes such as social innovation, social inclusion, entrepreneurship, culture and creativity, circular economy, temporary urbanism and more, the three projects pursued the ultimate ambition of creating a network of Innovative, Inclusive and Creative Hubs with shared objectives and desired impacts that can show viable ways forward towards the transition to resilient, inclusive and vibrant cities across Europe.

1. **CENTRINNO**: New CENTRalities in INdustrial areas as engines for inNOvation and urban transformation. <https://centrinno.eu/>

2. **T-FACTOR**: Unleashing future-facing urban hubs through culture and creativity-led strategies of transformative time. <https://www.t-factor.eu/>

3. **HUB-IN**: Hubs of Innovation and Entrepreneurship for the Transformation of Historic Urban Areas. <https://hubin-project.eu/>

Through this empowered Network of Hubs of Innovation and cities, the SPs have collected extensive knowledge, gathered experience and tested a variety of solutions and tools. The joint learnings of the three projects has been distilled in this Policy Report, which is

Figure 1 - Cities involved as pilot location

- CENTRINNO in blue
- T-FACTOR in red
- HUB-IN in green

- | | | | |
|---------------|-----|-----------------------|-----|
| 1. Amsterdam | ● ● | 14. Lisbon | ● ● |
| 2. Angouleme | ● | 15. Lodz | ● |
| 3. Barcelona | ● ● | 16. London | ● |
| 4. Belfast | ● | 17. Marseille | ● |
| 5. Bilbao | ● | 18. Milan | ● ● |
| 6. Blondous | ● | 19. New York | ● |
| 7. Brasov | ● | 20. Nicosia | ● |
| 8. Copenhagen | ● | 21. Paris | ● |
| 9. Dortmund | ● | 22. Shanghai | ● |
| 10. Florence | ● | 23. Slovenka Bistrica | ● |
| 11. Geneve | ● | 24. Tallinn | ● |
| 12. Genova | ● | 25. Utrecht | ● |
| 13. Kaunas | ● | 26. Zagreb | ● |

able to provide Policy Recommendations solidly based on a wide and varied range of local experiences.

Target and objectives of the Policy Report

This policy report makes use of the learnings from Horizon 2020 CENTRINNO, T-Factor and HUB-IN projects aiming to provide guidance in the implementation of heritage-driven urban regeneration approaches by making cities more creative, resilient, and innovative. More specifically, the experiences collected, the challenges, reflections and policy recommendations aim to:

- Demonstrate the need to strengthen culture-led urban regeneration policy to unlock and boost local economies and new models of innovation.
- Support policy makers in understanding the value of cultural heritage and its potential as a productive circular factor in a social entrepreneurship context.
- Drive better policy-making rooted in evidence and lessons learnt across regulatory, governance, funding, and civic participation and engagement challenges.

- Enable stakeholders to influence the development of culture-led urban regeneration policies conducive to more sustainable and creative historic urban areas.

The target audience of the Policy Report includes policy makers, from European institutions as well as local, regional, and national governments. However, the Policy Report also intends to reach out to stakeholders from the third and fourth sector, as well as SMEs to guide them through the logics of similar urban regeneration processes. Moreover, the evidence-based knowledge collected in the report aims to inform academia, research & innovation centres, providing analytical material based on a large sample of concrete project implementations.

Methodology and outline of the Policy Report

This document is the last milestone of a series of Clustering Activities that constituted the roadmap for this final compendium throughout the lifespan of the three SPs:

1. **The Action Plan** identified the main activities and shared outputs to be produced in this common journey.
2. **The Manifesto** introduced the general framework and key objectives of the SPs;
3. **The Clustering Meetings** and workshops brought together the tangible local experiences and provided a room for exchange, cross-learning and upscaling of the wide array of solutions proposed locally.

This Policy Report is the result of a research methodology that included activities carried out internally in each of the three consortiums and public events, all aiming to collect, analyse and disseminate the project experiences implemented locally.

Each project addressed its specificities and built up its own perspective, as well as its own discoveries and innovation paths. There is rich diversity in terms of cities and areas targeted, thematic foci, sectors addressed, solutions, methods and tools, as well as expertise and disciplinary domains at stake. Nevertheless, such diversity enriched the joint experience with shared and mutually reinforcing strategies to create more resilient, innovative cities, while ultimately informing and influencing policy making at EU level.

The results of this research and exchange processes are articulated in this Policy Report as follows:

1. This introduction;
2. Operationalising the Manifesto: the section describes what it meant to translate the key objectives and leading principles into concrete pilot actions, including the analysis of the operational challenges encountered;
3. Drivers of change: this section identifies nine policy areas that currently show gaps and blockages towards the operationalisation of innovative and experimental projects;
4. Policy Recommendations: This section proposes our policy recommendations for each of the policy areas identified, each supported by three pilot story examples, one from each of the SPs.

The individual experiences collected by each project across the local pilot experiences are distilled in this report into policy recommendations and showcased by concrete examples. The knowledge material available in this Policy Report synthesises a unique portfolio of innovations for urban regeneration driven by heritage, culture, creativity and encompassing aspirations of more just, sustainable and inclusive cities and communities.

2 - Operationalising the Manifesto

The three Sister Projects **CENTRINNO**, **HUB-IN**, and **T-FACTOR** share a set of goals and ambitions that are illustrated in the joint **Manifesto** "[Towards innovative, inclusive and creative hubs in European cities](#)".

This section first provides an overview of the common objectives of the three projects and of what it means to translate them into operational actions. The report then outlines the main challenges faced by the projects in putting such objectives to the ground, and clusters them by thematic field, in order to set a common ground for the development of joint policy recommendations for the regeneration of Historic Urban Areas and cultural landscapes across European cities.

2.1 The Manifesto in Practice

This section recalls the six objectives of the Manifesto and particularly emphasises their operational implications.

1. Innovative hubs and heritage-driven urban regeneration have the potential to unlock alternative economies and support human development.

Urban regeneration processes can boost new skills and knowledge, thus linking local communities and their economy to societal challenges. This mission envisions a better alignment of agendas and objectives across government, industry, society and environment so as to ensure a just transition. It means addressing the fundamental point of what democracy and democratic access to cities represent in today's societies, and how we can build collective capacity, agency and legitimacy throughout transition journeys. It also means facilitating citizens' access to opportunities for upskilling, reskilling and capacity building, as well as the creation of urban multipurpose hubs to plant seeds of innovation for alternative economies. For such multidisciplinary configurations to prosper, it requires not only the engagement of a mix of stakeholders across the quadruple helix, based on informal and convivial settings, but also a wider civic engagement and participation.

2. New urban regeneration models are tested and prototyped through networks of innovative hubs in different European cities, developing examples and methods for the future of other cities

Exchanging methods and approaches to urban regeneration and relevant learning across cities allows local practices to be analysed, compared, transferred and eventually scaled-up. Setting up effective networks of collaboration and creating synergies require the exploration of novel, wider forms of partnerships among European hubs serving as living laboratories. Here, novel forms of local economy and value creation can be unleashed around a variety of assets that stand at the foundation of our common wealth, such as streets and squares, energy grids, green and blue infrastructure, digital networks, educational and healthcare infrastructure, and many others. They explore strategies for sustainable development, community empowerment, green infrastructure, affordable housing, novel technologies, circular economy principles, and other innovative concepts.

This process benefits from triggering the interest of public officials and business representatives, bringing them on site, and stimulating their sense of participation. Once this cross-pollination is achieved, all actors involved shall have the will and means to bring the local experience to a European dimension.

3. Civil society and bottom-up processes can lead to productive and collaborative communities that play a key role in the transformation of Historic Urban Areas and cultural landscapes

Co-creation and participatory processes involving local communities bring in wider expertise, foster more experimentation while building agency and legitimacy for change in urban transformations. Favouring bottom-up engagement entails curating events and platforms (physical and digital) in which public authorities can meet citizens and professionals, but also institutionalise mechanisms (participatory budgeting, living labs methodologies, citizens assemblies, and more) that enable citizen participation and shared decision-making in urban regeneration strategies, plans and processes. Facilitating the creation of citizen associations and collective forms of ownership of urban hubs, through local authorities' endorsement, is also key to stimulate a culture of creative collaboration while demonstrating the co-benefits of open spaces designed and managed for this purpose.

4. The development potential of heritage and local culture is key to co-define alternative economies

Understanding heritage and identity both in their material and immaterial aspects is key to inspire and drive urban regeneration models that can unleash novel forms of shared public value. In order for cities to connect their existing and emerging values to their history and identity, it requires citizen engagement in policy decisions concerning urban development plans of post-industrial sites, the co-creative and agile use of abandoned spaces, the revitalisation of empty buildings and green assets and other heritage transformation opportunities. To fuel truly innovative urban regeneration processes it is also key to re-orient the provision of local services through new technology and maker practices. However, innovation per se is not a guarantee of success. In fact, greater opportunities lie where these urban processes manage to intercept and transform the local traditions and where the memory and identity are actualised and projected through participatory forms of cultural regeneration. as drivers for new circular productions and alternative economic modes.

5. Sustainable urban transformations must be rooted in the endogenous potential of Historic Urban Areas and cultural landscapes

Understanding the potential of material and immaterial resources available, spaces, and knowledge is key if we are to unlock sustainable, restorative and regenerative urban environments. The endogenous social, economic and environmental capital of urban areas should be leveraged to achieve the just transition, which entails radically redesigning the ways in which we consume, produce, and overall live. It is also crucial that this transition is orchestrated and governed by governance structures and arenas that are able to represent and include diverse perspectives, local knowledge, and ensure that the transition process is responsive to the needs and aspirations of different groups.

6. The long-term sustainability of new alternative economies and novel urban regeneration models in Historic Urban Areas and cultural landscapes relies on strong international networks

Governance structures ensuring wide local participation yet open to international experiences and influences are key to advance new models and approaches of urban regeneration and just transition. In order to ensure the intake and mutual learning of experiences from abroad it is crucial to transpose local lessons into internationally relevant content. It is equally important to actively seek and connect fellow local hubs' experiences through online channels, but also to connect local objectives of small-scale interventions (such as creative hubs) with already existing and well established cities' networks (such as C40 Cities, Cities Mission, Eurocities, etc..) where municipalities and policy makers are already on board.

2.2 Operational Challenges

The ground experience of the three Sister Projects unveiled a set of common challenges that belong to the experimental nature and innovation character of these urban regeneration processes.

Heritage value and innovation

Addressing goals of heritage-driven regeneration and innovation is both a challenge and an opportunity for many European cities. Nonetheless, the process typically starts with challenges related to understanding the intrinsic value of heritage and its combination with the innovation readiness/momentum:

- Mapping and capturing the variety of past and present local traditions that could inspire innovation, often results in an incomplete assessment due to lack of data and difficulties in reaching out to the key stakeholders, thereby introducing a selection bias to the process.
- The institutionalisation of new methods to assess and estimate attachment and emotional aspects of the heritage value may find resistance in current practice.
- Difficult to initiate and maintain synergies of cooperation or partnerships between traditional actors in the area and the pioneers bringing innovation to the local ecosystem.
- Difficulties with drawing a link of continuity between traditional knowledge available in the historical and cultural heritage and the resources needed for present and future innovation actions.
- Lack of a standardised practice on key indicators that would allow assessing and identifying key value of heritage in urban regeneration, and the potential outcomes of innovation practices.

Policy-making mindsets

The support of local policy makers is essential to provide fertile ground for urban innovation processes in experimentation settings. Gathering and keeping policy-making support deals with:

- The prioritisation of short-term effects that often drives decisions of the political cycle may limit strategic thinking for envisioning results beyond the project life.
- The interest of policy makers towards innovation is subject to instability and uncertainty, thus limiting the possibility of catalysing other actors' interest around a shared objective.
- The frequent risk-averse approach and consequent reluctance to embrace change by public administrations often gets reinforced by the need to find compromises for local decision-making. Such a constrained and compromise-oriented decision-making process may risk limiting the innovation momentum, especially when the experimental nature affects the predictability of project outcomes.
- The legitimacy and support from local authorities may be softened or interrupted by sudden priority shifts in policy-making or governmental changes.
- There is a weak political representation and limited resonance of the stakeholders in the innovation ecosystem, due to the lack of a critical mass and lobbying organisations to push these projects in the policy agenda setting.
- Limited presence of the innovation culture as an intrinsic and mainstreamed value of local administration, which often remains linked to the lifecycle of single projects.

Contingency and macro trends

Local regeneration processes are also influenced by exogenous factors and events happening at a broader scale:

- Global events, such as pandemics, wars, and economic crises can provoke sudden shifts in priorities, thereby threatening ongoing projects. Such global trends may also have negative effects on the establishment and consolidation of international networks.
- Systemic challenges at societal level often have place-specific cascading impacts at city level that require the adoption of non-tested, unplanned, and non-budgeted adaptation and mitigation measures.
- Uncertainties generated by macro trends, and their cascading local impacts are hard to embed in programming and analysing both baseline and foresight scenarios. This insecurity can affect the commitment of local actors to invest in innovation processes.
- Among place-specific contingencies, the uncertainty generated by real estate market fluctuations often represents a recurring challenge for the implementation of project activities and local actors' investments.

Spatial Planning and Urban Development Frameworks

The development and mainstreaming of innovation processes in Historic Urban Areas and cultural landscapes may be faced by different operational challenges at both planning and process levels:

- Traditional spatial planning practice, including urban planning, zoning and heritage preservation, brings along a long-established set of protocols and regulations that may limit cities and project's capacity of innovation and experimentation.
- Pilot actions alone struggle to determine lasting changes or a paradigm shift in consolidated local development models. The mainstreaming of pilot experimental approaches would require follow-up and scaling-up actions that struggle to permeate the currently established frameworks.
- Initiatives to introduce and adapt experimental planning approaches or new models for urban innovation within an already formalised decision-making framework, may be welcomed with caution or scepticism in the local stakeholder's ecosystem.
- Lack of strategies, policies, and planning practices to regulate temporary use of space in the longer term, thus making creative and circular uses of land a circumscribed and limited experience. The current frameworks are particularly weak on the opportunities to design longer (or to extend) agreements, which would allow for envisioning durable and self-sustainable projects.
- Innovation typically requires rapid and adaptive changes that mainstream urban planning and development models and practices are barely able to allow. This makes it difficult to embed fast-paced innovation processes in a framework of consolidated urban development practices and procedures.
- Limited availability of relevant local data, which would allow for analytical benchmarking and facilitate the replicability of successful regeneration examples.
- Transferring model practices and project experiences to a different local context often requires complex adaptation processes to the receiving planning environment.

Regulation

Existing regulatory frameworks may pose a wide range of challenges to the implementation of innovative regeneration strategies. Their experimental nature implies they explore a non-fully normed regulatory context where cases of discontinuity/incompatibility may arise. The shared understanding on regulatory challenges hints at:

- Regulatory steps and procedural requirements sometimes absorb significant time, resources and energies, thereby risking to reduce the effort devoted to the actual implementation of innovative solutions.
- Existing local and national regulations may define rather consolidated frameworks that limit or constrain the margin of flexibility needed for testing new approaches, especially in very innovative settings where continuous changes and adaptations are intrinsically part of the experimentation process.

The limited experience with experimental approaches undermines local administrators' capacity to assess needs and promote regulatory updates and innovation.

Funding

The challenges in this section relate both to the availability and access conditions for funding and to the flexibility of spending criteria. This report identifies common challenges in:

- The complexity of project applications and lack of dedicated staff limits local administrations capacities to secure financial resources.
- The complexity of administrative steps in the implementation coupled with the extra care required to avoid mistakes in reporting, challenges the ability of project actors to actually spend budgeted resources within the time frame of eligibility.
- Spending criteria often lack flexibility to accommodate unplanned needs and priorities that may emerge during implementation.
- Project budgets are fixed months ahead the start and cannot be increased to adjust to the contingencies (e.g., inflation, raw material price shocks, real estate market sudden fluctuations). This situation threatens many projects with emerging costs throughout the implementation, thus requiring change of project activities or serious uncertainty over the expected returns on the investments.
- Private investors struggle in obtaining public incentives and envisioning returns due to the lack of foreseeable economic gains. This uncertainty makes it difficult to mobilise large amounts of resources that would be a crucial enabling factor for sustainable innovation processes.
- Large and well experienced developers and stakeholders typically hold capacities and resources that often allow them to be more competitive in public tenders, whereas small innovators with a lower set of technical and administrative resources may struggle to compete in this environment. This partial asymmetry may reduce chances for non-conventional proposals and pioneering innovators to raise public interest and access projects in the regeneration process.

Knowledge

The availability of specialised knowledge and skills at the local scale is among the key enabling factors fostering project success, and securing these competences may bring with it a number of challenges:

- Misalignment between the timeline of project implementation and the time needed to build, acquire, and/or transfer knowledge and to train project staff for skills that are specifically required by the related innovation ecosystem.
- Limited availability of dedicated spaces, training material and frameworks to experiment and test new types of knowledge.
- Mismatch between the strict requirements of economic rentability principles and the need to experiment new sources of knowledge and train project specific skills with a degree of uncertainty over the expected financial returns.
- Lack of suitable formats (channels) to timely transfer the emerging skills and knowledge collected across different pilot experimentations, as well as difficulties to communicate new knowledge in a way that is meaningful to the variety of different actors in the ecosystem.
- Difficulties with the creation of a common base integrating different knowledge types (qualitative vs quantitative), and a set of technical and soft skills, all across different thematic areas.
- Lack of validated frameworks for learning recognition of social action and socially engaged practices often stands as a barrier to reciprocal and rewarding engagement, especially for young people.

Capacities

Besides the availability of a shared set of skills and knowledge in the project ecosystem, the implementation requires operational capacities to foster the innovation process. Challenges in terms of capacity relate to:

- Limited presence of project specific capacities and skills at local scale, especially in high experimentation environments, requires additional resources to hire external specialised experts.
- Limited availability of highly specialised professionals and often their geographic concentration, hinders the possibility for a wider set of local administrations to rely on their expertise.
- The multi-disciplinarity of thematic expertise and the different professional profiles and backgrounds of the actors involved pose challenges in facilitating dialogue and co-creation. While this stakeholder diversity within pilot actions holds great potential, it is more difficult to foster their interaction towards finding convergence and compromise solutions.
- New exploratory concepts and practices are not yet fully defined and consolidated by their “pioneers”, thus making their communication to the local sub-networks and the large public less effective.
- Language and communication barriers may constitute additional challenges in international projects, especially where new concepts emerge at pilot level that are not yet widely validated, and their definition is bound to contextual specificities and jargon.
- Limited experience with experimental approaches to urban regeneration embeds low capacities of local administrations to generate and support innovation, and enable flexibility in implementation.

Engagement

Engaging a plurality of local actors into fully co-creative regeneration processes often adds on quality and value, while accelerating time to meaningful impact. Yet, the experimental nature of the projects entails facing a set of significant challenges:

- The lack of clear returns, predictable outcomes and the diversity of expectations at play often affect the willingness of relevant actors to get engaged in activities they are not yet familiar with.
- Different or contrasting expectations between actors involved in the project and external stakeholders with interests in the project area may originate conflicts throughout the engagement process.
- Reaching a synthesis on the attachment and estimation of the value local communities attribute to cultural heritage is a hard task, especially when trying to predict the unintended social consequences of their regeneration processes.
- It is difficult for project leaders to find the optimal balance between their top-down influence (and project specific bias) and bottom-up contributions (by local stakeholders external to the project) envisaged by the engagement effort.
- Local stakeholders willing to be involved are often familiar actors that are already involved with other engagement initiatives in the same environment. It is difficult to go beyond that core group and reach other relevant groups (e.g. young people, minorities, etc.)
- The burden of numerous events, the frequent engagement attempts, and the uncertainty over expected returns often contribute to create participation and consultation fatigue. The fatigue bias, thus the low stimulation to actively participate, affects the ability to catch interests, highlight project opportunities and facilitate synergies among local stakeholders.

3 - Drivers of Change

Experiences from the three Sister Projects and the identification of common challenges in the implementation enabled a cross-project reflection on the crucial role of the policy arena in urban regeneration processes. The analysis and systematisation of the challenges led to the identification of nine policy areas that currently show gaps and blockages towards the operationalisation of innovative and experimental projects in historic urban areas and cultural landscapes. Namely:

1. Administrative procedures and planning frameworks

This policy area refers to the wide set of administrative procedures, decision making protocols and planning tools that govern the implementation of innovative regeneration processes.

2. Governance structures for multi-stakeholder participation

This policy area covers governance models, co-creation frameworks and partnership arrangements between public administrators and local communities that shall foster participatory innovation from design throughout implementation.

3. Alternative financing models

This policy area covers the accessibility to potential or existing financial schemes that are able to fuel continuous innovation and alternative financing models that have recently gained traction as a way to secure funding, stimulate experimentation and engage local communities.

4. Project resilience mechanisms

This policy area covers all mitigation measures aiming to strengthen resilience and adaptation of innovative projects to unexpected contingencies and exogenous trends or shocks.

5. Policy transfer & mainstreaming processes

This policy area concerns all the mechanisms and practices designed to facilitate policy transfer among different cities, and the measures promoting replication, re-adaptation and mainstreaming of impactful project activities from elsewhere.

6. Knowledge transfer and capacity building

This policy area concerns all aspects related to the communication, dissemination and diffusion of innovative knowledge, training, and capacity-building, involving local stakeholders and administrators.

7. Networks of innovation & communities of practice

This policy area relates to the measures that sustain the creation, valorisation and strengthening of innovation networks and communities of practice, in ways that unleash vibrant ecosystems of knowledge sharing and practice exchange.

8. Advocacy, influence capacity & communication

This policy area relates to the initiatives and measures aimed at building advocacy and increasing the influence capacity of stakeholders and local actors towards the wide public and the policy arenas.

9. Impact assessment methods

This policy area refers to the principles and methods used to assess and evaluate the impact of innovative urban regeneration processes.

4 - Policy Recommendations

1. Administrative procedures and planning frameworks

Endorse urban strategies and action plans to enable the utilisation of historical buildings and urban areas for innovative and experimental initiatives aimed at preserving and enhancing both tangible and intangible local heritage

2. Governance structures for multi-stakeholder participation

Establish permanent multi-stakeholder (digital and physical) forums, working groups and participatory decision-making processes that encourage active participation and engagement from all corners of society.

3. Alternative financing models

Support experimental projects towards inclusive bottom-up innovation and less profitability-based competition, especially in the long-term access to land and public spaces.

4. Project resilience mechanisms

Introduce flexibility schemes, management mechanisms and pre-defined protocols to deal with uncertainty since the project call (or proposal) phase.

5. Policy transfer & mainstreaming processes

Support policy transfer and adaptation through peer-exchange mechanisms based on a common repository of best practices.

6. Knowledge transfer and capacity building

Promote distributed opportunities of lifelong learning and vocational training on innovative skills that are relevant and transferable to a diversity of contexts.

7. Networks of innovation & communities of practice

Create a long-lasting community around the local regeneration process by offering a platform (digital and physical) for different stakeholders to co-design and participate in local development processes.

8. Advocacy, influence capacity & communication

Provide citizens, stakeholders, and decision-makers with direct access to knowledge, best-practices and hands-on demonstrators by organising open workshops, residencies and events with international/high-level guests, to showcase model experiences and success stories.

9. Impact assessment methods

Establish a common yet adaptable framework for monitoring and evaluating the impact of innovation and entrepreneurship to focus on the qualitative assessment of the transformation achieved, beyond purely quantitative measurements and KPIs.

RECOMMENDATION #1

ENDORSE URBAN STRATEGIES AND ACTION PLANS TO ENABLE THE UTILISATION OF HISTORICAL BUILDINGS AND URBAN AREAS FOR INNOVATIVE AND EXPERIMENTAL INITIATIVES AIMED AT PRESERVING AND ENHANCING BOTH TANGIBLE AND INTANGIBLE LOCAL HERITAGE.

[Policy Area: Administrative procedures and planning frameworks]

The valorisation of heritage requires a continuous, participatory development process, targeting the use of space and the creation (or consolidation) of sustainable activities, that is tightly anchored within regulatory and planning frameworks at city level. The commitment to action plans and strategies specifically targeting experimental practices for the use of heritage spaces would be a key enabler of wider and self-sustained innovation. Action plans need to include specific regulatory provisions for heritage regeneration, following a revision of those administrative procedures that currently represent barriers or limiting factors. The adoption of dedicated action plans can be a catalyst for engaging a wider pool of actors, thereby nurturing the co-design of new solutions that can amend rigid planning frameworks. New action plans and strategies should also be able to speed up decision making processes and protocols, including by adopting more flexibility in budget allocation criteria and eligibility of project implementation activities.

CREATIVE URBAN ENVIRONMENTS ON THE POLITICAL AGENDA

[Copenhagen Pilot / CENTRINNO]

Main Objectives

- Retention of existing creative urban environments
- Development of new creative urban environments

Solution

Place creative urban environments on the political agenda and create a pool to support local initiatives

Actors Involved

Local actors (creative businesses, organisations and institutions), developers working in the area, different stakeholders at multiple levels and areas of expertise within the municipality.

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- Timing and knowledge of the windows of opportunity in policy development
- Robust relations within the municipality
- Supporting agenda with data and analysis
- Communicating it through relations building and events

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[CENTRINNO Framework](#)

A city-wide mapping of resources has been conducted analysing the number and sizes of creative businesses and craft trades in Copenhagen as well as the development in rental prices. This analysis has formed the basis for a municipal report on creative industries that preceded the Municipal Plan Strategy making it possible to introduce the issue in the final strategy.

The analysis has underlined the need for policy measures, and the challenges and possible actions has been included in the Municipal Plan Strategy. Consequently, concrete initiatives are expected to be included in the final Municipal Plan e.g. by developing the concept of creative zones.

Other insights from CENTRINNO have resulted in initiatives and strategies: Most importantly the coming Business Strategy, where access to space for creatives and crafts is expected to be a priority as well as a new municipal fund for creative businesses and urban environments.

The fund provides grants for projects and initiatives that contributes to developing Copenhagen as a creative city. The fund for creative industries and urban environments pays out DKK 1.35 million (~180.000€) annually in 2023 and 2024 for strategic development of creative urban environments and general support for creative professions. This can be done, for example, through partnerships on new lighthouse projects that profile the capital, or through the development of local activities that support general business development.

CENTRINNO has made an imprint on the coming Municipal Plan Strategy ensuring political attention to the subject. A municipal fund for 'creative businesses and urban environments' has been established.

FRAMEWORK FOR A FULL CONNECTED BELFAST WATERFRONT PROMENADE

[Belfast Pilot / HUB-IN]

Main Objectives

- Prioritise pipeline projects that will best support and shape the development of Belfast's waterfront
- Recommend potential delivery models including innovative solutions to advance this development
- Identify potential sources of funding.

Solution

Establish a longer-term framework for the development of Belfast Maritime Mile – where heritage and community underpin and support development, technology and regeneration

Actors Involved

Leader: Maritime Belfast Trust

Partner Organisations: Belfast Waterfront Task Group, Belfast City Council and Public sector (including the Department of Community, Department for the Economy and the Department of Infrastructure)

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- Secure match funding, promote tender widely.
- Collaborate for data on developments.
- Engage applicants broadly, leverage experts.
- Ensure alignment with HUB-IN goals

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[HUB-IN Belfast Action Plan](#)

The Belfast HUB-IN place is located at the city's iconic Maritime Mile, the city's historic waterfront. The Framework will ensure the recovery of its cultural heritage, underpinning a clear sense of local identity of the city's waterfront and will provide stakeholders such as developers, creatives, landowners and local communities with a clear long-term vision to work towards. It will be the first time the area has a shared vision across multiple landowners, business and community interests and heritage providers.

The strategic framework is focused on enabling a promenade along the waterfront on both sides of and across the water. This framework encourage usage by residents and visitors, engendering vibrancy and vitality. The framework enhances the opportunities for Challenge Fund applicants to understand the future aspiration for the Maritime Mile and will stimulate their approach to the development of their projects.

This Framework aligns with HUB-IN objective of reversing the trends of abandonment and neglect of historic heritage in urban areas and landscapes and recover cultural heritage values in the Historic Urban Area with a sense of local identity. It also achieves the local outcome of supporting the [Maritime Mile](#) to become a place that is inclusive and accessible to local communities and where people will want to spend time.

Results achieved:

Providing challenge fund applicants with information and visualisation of the Belfast Waterfront promenade for the next 20 years, giving applicants a better understanding of the long-term aspirations of the area and where their projects could fit and support those aspirations.

TEMPORARY USE FRAMEWORK IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF KAUNAS INNOVATION PARK

[Kaunas Pilot / T-Factor]

Main Objectives

- Foster the spread of temporary uses as a viable tool for socially innovative, vibrant, and sustainable urban regeneration.
- Provide developers with guidelines and recommendations to encourage temporary uses throughout the development of the Kaunas Aleksotas Industry Innovation Park (KAIP)
- Encourage and sustain citizens engagement and participation throughout the development of the KAIP

Solution

The concept of SANDBOX Business Model provides a strategy for Kaunas Fortress Park to become an integrated part of the KAIP as a buffer space as well as creating and offering new supportive actions/services for innovation communities to come

Actors Involved

Municipality of Kaunas, Kaunas University of Technology, Kaunas Fortress Park, Kaunas IN, KTU National Innovation and Entrepreneurship Centre (NIEC)

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

Activating the nearby areas through infrastructuring can be an effective strategy to generate interest and create a sense of community. Hosting Temporary Uses the surrounding areas can be transformed into a vibrant and engaging environment that could eventually support the development site.

T-Factor Kaunas Pilot conducted interviews and meetings with the key stakeholders such as the Municipality of Kaunas, Kaunas IN and KTU National Innovation and Entrepreneurship Centre (NIEC), which has led to the formation of concept notes for the sandbox business model. While developing a theoretical model canvas, a few testing activities took place. During the BiodiverCities I workshop and the Creative Design Objects initiative, the academic community could test their prototypes in the Kaunas Fortress Park, which is essential to make further development and next steps in the researched topic. It also contributes to a better overview on how the area could be used as a Sandbox, what potentials and weaknesses it contains. This Sandbox model is foreseen as the main legacy of the Kaunas Pilot which will enable the continuity of meanwhile uses as a tool for social innovation and urban regeneration.

The main change which led to the more extensive influence of T-Factor is the integration of the Kaunas Fortress Park (neighbouring the KAIP) as the potential contributor to urban regeneration.

RECOMMENDATION #2

ESTABLISH PERMANENT MULTI-STAKEHOLDER (DIGITAL AND PHYSICAL) FORUMS, WORKING GROUPS AND PARTICIPATORY DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES THAT ENCOURAGE ACTIVE PARTICIPATION AND ENGAGEMENT FROM ALL CORNERS OF SOCIETY.

[Policy Area: Governance models for multi-stakeholder collaboration]

Civic engagement in urban regeneration processes requires structured spaces and opportunities of participation that are inclusive, accessible, and designed well beyond pure consultation purposes. Such spaces and opportunities should be designed as participatory platforms that leverage both physical and digital environments to engage a wide range of actors, in ways that encourage and sustain bottom up and inclusive contributions regardless of age, digital preparedness and objectives. These open platforms (permanent forums, agoras and working groups) should be distinctively characterised by easy accessibility and accompanied by a proactive effort for wider inclusiveness (also through incentives and rewards schemes for participation) in order to engage a more varied social milieu and fuel the co-design empowerment (agency) in local communities.

PERMANENT PLATFORMS FOR MULTI-STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT & PARTICIPATION

[Paris Pilot / CENTRINNO]

Main Objectives

- Engage a large spectrum of actors from the civil society, the third sectors and the involvement of public authorities
- Develop joint projects on distributed production, and vocational training courses on circular design and food production

Solution

Opening three creative and productive spaces across the city and connect them to a distributed city-level ecosystem of platforms for training and public debates on the productive and sustainable city focusing on food and urban agriculture.

Actors Involved

Volumes an SME focused on the design of creative and productive third-party places

Fabcity Grand Paris an association to implement the Fab City vision in the Greater Paris area

Oasis21, a cooperative community-oriented enterprise

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- Financial accessibility of real estate market
- Ensure support by local authorities
- Demonstrating the sustainability of alternative economic models

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[CENTRINNO Fab City Hub Toolkit](#)

The establishment of a Fabcity Hub in Paris's North-east district, guided by CENTRINNO principles, posed significant challenges. Creative and sustainable economy professionals were attracted through extensive networks and support from the City of Paris. Oasis 21 facilitated community integration via partnerships with local associations and diverse events.

To ensure economic sustainability, coworking spaces were prioritized, along with collaborations with training programs. The addition of a Foodlab and small food-related businesses enriched the hub's values. Integration into a larger ecosystem led by Oasis 21, comprising three interconnected sites, promoted cooperation and participative governance, strengthening a shared commitment to sustainability.

Results achieved:

By adopting a strong identity focused on the social economy and ecological transition, Oasis 21 and its partners have succeeded in bringing together members and residents who share the same values, which has boosted knowledge sharing.

By creating a dedicated animation strategy involving consistent topics (urban agriculture, circular economy, DIY,...), the Fabcity Hub Paris gained legitimacy amongst a larger audience as a beacon for these alternatives.

By choosing a cooperative model with a shared governance involving various stakeholders, the Fabcity Hub Paris and the cooperative Oasis 21 showed that another path than capital based models is possible.

BLUEPRINTS FOR WIDELY APPLICABLE HUBS' GOVERNANCE STRUCTURES

[Utrecht Pilot / HUB-IN]

Main Objectives

- Create and exchange insights on good governance between various hubs in the city insights on good governance of hubs
- Create a template governance structure/DIY toolkit that can be applied in existing and future hubs

Solution

Generate a governance structure blueprint and accompanying DIY toolkit that the municipality of Utrecht can use to reorganize current cultural hubs and create new sustainable governance structures in future (Historical Urban Area) hubs.

Actors Involved

Coordination: Municipality of Utrecht
External Experts (consultation process); Domplein 4 Tenants (decisions on governance model); Other Hubs (knowledge exchange activities)

Feasibility Conditions

- Enhance tenant collaboration and financial sustainability within cultural hubs.
- Utilize innovative governance models, a universal template, and a hands-on toolkit to refine cultural hub management

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[HUB-IN Utrecht Action Plan](#)

The goal is to generate learnings for hubs in the Werkspoorkwartier in Utrecht, by creating a governance structure blueprint and accompanying DIY toolkit that the municipality of Utrecht can use to reorganize current cultural hubs and create new sustainable governance structures in future hubs in the Historical Urban Area (HUA).

In order to do so, the Action will use insights acquired in the HUA, by setting-up knowledge sharing activities between Hubs of Innovation in Utrecht and by performing a case study of an existing hub outside the HUA that currently encounters governance issues, Domplein 4. This is an old heritage building in the centre of Utrecht, hosting a hub that contains several organizations; however, the parties located in the building encounter serious problems with regard to the structure of their collaboration within the hub, which is endangering the future of these parties in this building.

This action contributes to the preservation and creation of workspaces for creative entrepreneurs in the HUA, and support the creative industries in the HUA and the city at large. In this process, insights from the HUB-IN process and from cultural hubs in the HUA (and in Utrecht in general) will be used. Overall, the process can be understood as a feedback loop: knowledge acquired in the HUA and city is used in the case study, and the outcomes of the case study is shared with hubs in the HUA and the city.

A NEW PROOF OF CONCEPT TO FACILITATE MULTILAYER URBAN CO-CREATION

[Bilbao Pilot / T-Factor]

Main Objectives

- Create participatory and collaborative forms of neighbouring governance
- Create new dynamics for civic participation that detect civic actors that are already contributing to general wellbeing and help them scale or pass the torch
- Create proof of concept of new institutions that overcome Infrastructure-only inertia

Solution

The Civic Design Council involves representatives from local authorities, regeneration stakeholders, grassroots communities, and universities, and foster inclusive urban regeneration by articulating 'soft' forms of collaboration and co-creation that make the most of existing assets and resources in the area, and bridge the gap between knowledge and expertise at different levels

Actors Involved

Bilbao Ekintza, Espacio Open and Tecnalía; Universities, Students, Grassroot Initiatives, Neighbours/Civic Champions, T-Labs

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

Trust-building was key to engaging with local stakeholders. The construction of prototypes (tangible and real elements that directly benefit citizens) has been the catalyst for prototyping this proof of concept (collaborative governance).

Creating new models of relationships between institutions and organisations in the city to create a prosperous and sustainable urban future is no easy task. New models and ways of thinking require new approaches, but often these approaches are too abstract, difficult to understand and almost impossible to realise.

This was one of the first conclusions we came to when we started the T-Factor project, but we did not give up. We wanted to prototype new models of collaborative governance so, although it was difficult to count on the necessary agents due to the abstract nature of the concept, we set about developing prototypes that would solve specific problems of citizens with a co-creative approach.

We needed to create a community with the key agents of Zorrotzaurre and generate an environment of trust, so, through participatory design with universities, grassroots initiatives and the residents themselves, we identified needs in the Zorrotzaurre neighbourhood in the areas of Circular and Collaborative Economy, Climate Change and Resilient Cities and Sociality and Wellbeing.

We transformed these needs into challenges, and these challenges into ideas for solutions, and these ideas for solutions into prototypes. And it was by DOING that we inadvertently began to prototype new modes of collaborative governance in which we were able to mobilise resources, materials, procedures and knowledge to create more prosperous and sustainable cities.

This is how the Civic Design Council was created, the body that governs such prototypes but, once established, will carry out new projects with the same dynamics.

RECOMMENDATION #3

SUPPORT EXPERIMENTAL PROJECTS TOWARDS INCLUSIVE BOTTOM-UP INNOVATION AND LESS PROFITABILITY-BASED COMPETITION, ESPECIALLY IN THE LONG-TERM ACCESS TO LAND AND PUBLIC SPACES.

[Policy Area: Alternative financing models]

Financial schemes able to fuel continuous innovation and support urban regeneration experiences are key for long-term sustainability of innovative hubs. Tailored funding pools, partnerships and participatory budget forms represent key factors to activate and sustain the bottom-up nature of innovation. Smoothing project selection criteria towards greater social impact (less profitability-based competition) and more hands-on cooperation in design and implementation (less top-down monitoring) are important enabling factors for an inclusive innovation, along with simplified management and reporting protocols, as well as more adaptable spending criteria.

Difficulties in long term access to land and space, and the natural predominance of real estate market logics that drive prices, constitute important limiting factors. These obstacles call for the adoption of tailored schemes for granting affordable and long-term solutions in the use of land and public spaces for experimental project experiences. When time and property constraints are too rigid, unlocking more possibilities for flexible temporary uses of space can also make a decisive contribution to urban innovation.

TALLINN PARTICIPATORY BUDGET

[Tallinn Pilot / CENTRINNO]

Main Objectives

- Creating a platform for the emergence of ideas from communities;
- Raising citizen awareness of how local governments are managed
- Making the residents think and act together, increasing coherency and a sense of community

Solution

Participatory budget means that all residents of Tallinn can submit public use and free to access ideas to their community that could be established with the city's money.

Actors Involved

Community representatives (propose project ideas), a special committee (shortlists proposals) and community (votes shortlisted proposals), District Governments (implements selected idea), the City Government (finances the participatory budget).

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

The main condition is the political will of the city government and the city council, and the financing of the participatory budget. One of the lessons learnt is that such projects need huge amount of communication support to reach citizens, both in the ideas presentation and voting phase.

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

CENTRINNO Fab City Hub Toolkit

Participatory budget means that all residents of Tallinn can submit ideas to their community that could be established with the city's money. The money from the participatory budget can only be used for facilities that are meant for public use and free to access.

An expert committee will evaluate the feasibility of the ideas submitted and the best ones will be introduced, discussed, and put up for public vote. In accordance with the conditions of the participatory budget, each city district has the option to carry out one project a year, which the residents of the city districts have submitted, and which has gained the most votes.

The popularity of bottom-up community activities has intensified in correlation with the success of the CENTRINNO Tallinn pilot. As the goal of the pilot was to create a functioning community hub into an abandoned cultural house in the district of North Tallinn, other city districts have also started to support more community activities. This, for example, is showcased in added communication support for the participatory budget so that as many people as possible would send in their ideas and, majority would cast their vote. Community centered approach is gaining more popularity by the year, and this is in part, thanks to CENTRINNO.

Results achieved:

The participatory budget was started in 2020 with 800 000€, 1M€ was planned for the participatory budget in 2022. In three years, 24 citizens ideas have been realized in the process. Ideas such as pumptracks, a community sauna, promenades and ski-jump towers are just a few that started from a citizens idea and have now been finalized.

MECHANISM OF SUPPORT FOR SMALL LOCAL PROJECTS

[Slovenska Bistrica Pilot / HUB-IN]

Main Objectives

- Enable communities to apply for organisational help and small financial contributions to implement a local action;
- Diminish the amount of unused and decayed urban places;
- Involve citizens / local communities in placemaking.

Solution

Creation of a mechanism of support for small local projects, stimulating various local stakeholders/initiatives to collectively implement actions that contribute to regeneration of rundown areas and to more vibrant public spaces

Actors Involved

Design of the mechanism: Municipality of SB, Tourist information centre, Development and Information Centre. Implementation: Municipality with support of a local NGO

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- Contingency fund for unforeseen space renovation costs.
- Encourage active users' council participation and coordination.
- Secure political commitment, leverage recent elections for stability

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[HUB-IN Slovenska Bistrica Action Plan](#)

The aim of this action is to accelerate urban regeneration of the historic city centre through participatory revitalisation approaches, such as for example placemaking, community co-creation, tactical urbanism, crowdsourcing and match-funding. The aim is to invite local creative communities to participate in the Historical Urban Area (HUA) revitalisation process in partnership with the Municipality, developing an inclusive HUA that will stimulate people to meet in it and develop new ties, which is, after all, an aim of every creative HUB – and particularly within HUB-IN's goals.

This mechanism of support for small local projects enables communities to apply for organisational help and small financial contributions to implement a small local action that they have proposed, from simple infrastructural improvements to organisation of community oriented free of charge events.

The action includes the following steps: 1.Design of the mechanism; 2.Open call for small local actions; 3.Coordination of small-scale actions implementation; 4.Review of the process and improved plan of the process for the next year.

If successful, the institutionalised placemaking mechanism has a potential of becoming a regular program commissioned by the municipality.

The expected short-term results include: 5 implemented small local actions; Implementation of the call and promotion of participative placemaking; Established relationship with 5 communities that implemented an action; Increased social capital at the local level; Increased level of trust between the Municipality and local (creative) communities; Increase in the use of spaces/places of HUA; New social infrastructure; Urban space regeneration

GRASSROOTS COORDINATION AND SUPPORT TO MEANWHILE FUNDING

[Euston-London Pilot / T-Factor]

Main Objectives

- Support existing community organisations and champions in accessing resources for neighbourhood improvements towards and safer more convivial streets and spaces,
- Foster a more synergistic and coordinated use of resources
- Build and develop capacity within existing community organisations

Solution

A 'Story Trail' that implements and connects site specific arts-led public realm improvements across Regents Park Estate, an area impacted by disruptive development. The trail will support wayfinding, promote community safety and increase access to green and open spaces across the neighbourhood.

Actors Involved

Initiation: Regents Park Estate Community Champions + local community organisations Fitsrovia Youth in Action and Old Diorama Arts Centre. Facilitation: University of the Arts London, Camden Council. Implementation: Local artists. Funding: HS2 and T-Factor

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

Collaboration with existing organisations. Iteration of tangible activities and outputs (prototyping approach). Connecting across scales/developers, local government officers and community organisations and residents. Aligning resident goals with dutyholder priorities.

After many engagement events and activities across the estate, supported by the community organisations and T Factor team, the Champions came up with the idea of a 'Story Trail' for Regents Park Estate. It will provide open space enhancements that support wayfinding and promote community safety, increasing access and use of green and open spaces across the area. Working together the community organisations and T Factor team have been able to bring the work of the Champions to the attention of the Euston Partnership and Camden Council teams working to improve the public realm in Regents Park Estate during ongoing disruptive development in the area. The partners have been able to support the Community Champions to align their proposals to the priorities of local duty-holders and secure funding for the project from a number of sources. A group of Community Curators is also being recruited to ensure hyper-local representation in the project leadership. A series of hyperlocal engagements are being delivered that are gathering stories of local ecology, culture and heritage and identifying sites of intervention. Sites, stories and ideas for improvements e.g. (lighting, signage, greening, etc) are being combined into 'briefs' to be shared via open call to commission artistic installations that will be connected to create the trail.

Results achieved:

£160,000 raised in funding for art-led public realm improvements. 3 part time jobs created linked to project delivery. Public realm improvements in Everton Mews. Engagement and activation events across the estate. Creation and consolidation of collaborative relationships between public, private and community organisations.

RECOMMENDATION #4

INTRODUCE FLEXIBILITY SCHEMES, MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS AND PRE-DEFINED PROTOCOLS TO DEAL WITH UNCERTAINTY SINCE THE PROJECT CALL (OR PROPOSAL) PHASE.

[Policy Area: Project resilience mechanisms]

The high degree of uncertainty deriving from both exogenous factors (e.g. Covid-19, Climate hazards and International conflicts) and endogenous dynamics (e.g. Real estate market, Inflation) calls for targeted plans and strategies to strengthen the resilience of innovative projects vis-à-vis rapid change. Given the difficulties to raise additional resources in the course of action, and the limited flexibility to divert from originally planned activities and budget allocations, pre-defined mechanisms and protocols to deal with uncertainty would be recommended. Resilience plans should contemplate the allocation of reserved budget resources as well as increased flexibility in budget spending (in case of non-planned conditions) to limit financial exposure, constraints on investments and the meaningful implementation of project activities. In parallel, the resilience plans shall be accompanied by pre-set management mechanisms and administrative protocols to deal with emerging uncertainty and activate mitigation strategies.

RENT-FREE MAKERSPACES AND COMMUNITY GARDENS ARE ON CITY PROPERTY

[Tallinn Pilot / CENTRINNO]

Main Objectives

- To allow the continuous expansion of community gardens and makerspaces in the city of Tallinn
- To ensure the sustainability of the system

Solution

Establishing community gardens and makerspaces on city premises to ensure their freedom from rent duties

Actors Involved

Community Gardens: City Council (allows free land), NGOs (land concessionaire), Community (maintenance), Tallinn Urban Environment and Public Works Department (finances the community gardens cost related activities from a specific measure).

Makerspaces: Tallinn Strategic Management Office (identifying suitable spots for makerspaces), Tallinn Waste Treatment Plots (places where the city has chosen to build makerspaces), makerspace masters and the community.

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

The main lesson learnt is that community centred activities need to be supported by the city – whether by giving free space, rooms, or direct financing. In the case of land and space already owned by the city, this adds zero costs to the city government and might even lower maintenance costs (the mowing and taking care of the areas is an obligation given to the community, thus does not have to be procured for). In return, it brings many benefits to the citizens and communities.

The first public makerspace of Tallinn was built on the premises of Kopli 93 community hub which has been brought to life under CENTRINNO project. The community hub started from an old cultural house, a community garden, community apiaries and only then a makerspace was added. With this, CENTRINNO gave a clear direction for other makerspaces in the city to be built as well. As our makerspace was built on the city premises, it made sense to add others as well on the city territory as in doing so, they become free of rent duty which is one of the most important restraints for establishing and sustaining a makerspace or a community garden in the long run.

With community gardens, the city council votes on giving the land for use for NGOs upkeeping the gardens for one year. Each year, this is voted on again, sometimes adding new community gardens to the list. With makerspaces, the city does not rent the spaces to NGOs, insteads creates city financed makerspaces for community to use into citys premises.

Results achieved:

30 community gardens have been established across Tallinn, and 8 makerspaces are being built now. Nearly 4000 regular visitors have been counted in the gardens, the data for the use of built or newly finished makerspaces is not available at the moment.

HUB-IN BUSINESS AND FINANCING MODELS GUIDE

[All Pilots & Alliance Cities / HUB-IN]

Main Objectives

- Provide guidance to the business and financing models landscape of heritage-led regeneration in Historic Urban Areas.
- Showcase European examples with several business and financing models.
- Provide inspiration with examples of good governance structures to attract financing and make business models work.

Solution

This guide presents modern business, financing & governance models for heritage-led urban renewal. Real European cases offer insights, while the Heritage Finance Ecosystem introduces diverse funding opportunities

Actors Involved

EU cities: Real cases insights based on data collected to HUB-IN Atlas. International experts: Connect their experiences with novel financing models to HUA heritage-led regeneration.

Feasibility Conditions

- Ensure the Guide Application in each city
- Empowers HUB-IN and follower cities to leverage collected case knowledge by using a complementary tool: [HUB-IN Interactive Dialogue Tool](#).

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[HUB-IN Business & Financing Models Guide](#)

This guide is part of the HUB-IN project, fostering innovation and entrepreneurship in Historic Urban Areas while preserving their unique identity. It showcases European cases of business, financing, and governance models that enable heritage-led regeneration. The Heritage Finance Ecosystem opens doors to funding opportunities. HUB-IN combines traditional public funding with crowdfunding for inclusive, sustainable development.

Based on data from the [HUB-IN Atlas](#), expert interviews, desk research, and the Community Finance Ecosystem, this guide explores how innovative actions fuel sustainable transformation. Operating through a network of hubs, HUB-IN incubates entrepreneurship, leveraging heritage as a catalyst for change, meeting resident needs, attracting investment, and improving lives.

The guide delves into the landscape of business, financing, and governance models for heritage-led regeneration. It is a cornerstone for historic urban areas aspiring to become HUB-IN places, preserving identities, fostering innovation, and regenerating sustainably. It accommodates various starting points, whether seeking public funds like European Structural Investment Funds or exploring business models for small community projects.

Results achieved:

Serving as inspiration for 8 innovation hubs in [pilot cities](#), per Action Plan, this guide benefits [HUB-IN Alliance](#) development. It fosters urban regeneration, offering practical insights and innovative models across European cities.

HUB-IN Business & Financing Models Guide

Including the HUB-IN Business & Financing Model Catalogues

T-FACTOR PORTFOLIO APPROACH

[Amsterdam, Bilbao, Kaunas, Lisbon, London, Milan / T-Factor]

Main Objectives

- Embrace a more flexible, iterative, and 'learning by doing & making' approach in urban regeneration
- Test multiple assumptions and options for inclusive, vibrant and sustainable placemaking
- Distribute the risk and mitigate risks of 'projectification'.

Solution

Design and delivery approach to temporary uses as a synergistic and coordinated set of spatial experiments that test different assumptions and hypothesis of placemaking

Actors Involved

Whole T-Factor Consortium and the local coalitions involved in the actual programmes of meanwhile placemaking

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- A portfolio approach requires time together with openness and capacity to engage with new mindsets and understandings of systemic changes.
- It is important to engage key regeneration stakeholders from the very beginning, in order to leverage strategic learning and assess the potential and viability of meanwhile uses in influencing long term paths of urban regeneration

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[T-Factor Toolbox](#)

In T-Factor, we adopted a portfolio approach to the design and delivery of meanwhile strategies. A number of specific missions were co-defined in each pilot context, and then explored through a portfolio of temporary experiments that could feed and reinforce each other along the missions and overall contribute to unleash multiple co-benefits. Working through a portfolio logic helped distribute the risk, engage with a plurality of communities, and strengthen opportunities of learning by doing and learning by making throughout a variety of bottom-up paths to sustainable, inclusive, and equitable urban regeneration.

Results achieved:

- More than 60 temporary experiments and activities in address to 16 local missions of innovations
- Strengthened participation and collaboration across different actors, with a key focus on vulnerable groups and communities that typically have less chances of active say in urban regeneration
- Contributed to demonstrate the value of synergistic and diversified meanwhile uses to address both existing and emerging needs.

RECOMMENDATION #5

SUPPORT POLICY TRANSFER AND ADAPTATION THROUGH PEER-EXCHANGE MECHANISMS BASED ON A COMMON REPOSITORY OF BEST PRACTICES.

[Policy Area: Policy transfer & mainstreaming processes]

The long-term success of urban regeneration processes rooted in heritage preservation and valorisation also depends on the continuity and institutionalisation of experimental project experiences. Policy transfer mechanisms are needed to facilitate wider adaptation and implementation of impactful projects both within countries (across municipalities and regions), but also beyond boundaries in a European framework of exchange. Similarly, mainstreaming procedures are needed to consolidate good practices and turn the positive impacts of experimental projects into business-as-usual practice for a long term development. The facilitation of policy transfer and mainstreaming mechanisms calls for a twofold intervention involving project actors and policy makers: a) on the one hand it is essential to enable peer exchange mechanisms among implementing actors, for instance by establishing a common repository of best practices; these need to be pre-arranged for replication by unpacking them into policy relevant thematic modules that facilitate their transferability. b) On the other hand, policy makers shall intervene at an administrative and regulatory level to simplify the adaptation of an original project experience (legislative framework and activities) to the place-specific needs of a different local context; this requires regulatory sandbox zones granting the flexibility needed to transfer and scale up.

CENTRINNO FOCUS GROUP WORKSHOP SERIES

[Project Level / CENTRINNO]

Main Objectives

- Dissemination of project experiences and pilot experimentations.
- Discussion and validation of CENTRINNO approaches and tools.
- Uptake of CENTRINNO tools and experiences in new contexts

Solution

Engage with external experts into the project concepts, tools and experiences to stimulate a cross-learning mechanism of feedback, improvements and uptake opportunities beyond CENTRINNO boundaries.

Actors Involved

CENTRINNO Coordination & Pilots; External Experts representing Policymakers, Local Authorities, SMEs, NGOs, Citizen's associations, Researchers, and Fab City Hubs from the enlarged-Europe and beyond

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

The network consolidated by CENTRINNO throughout the project cycle represented an important condition to establish the Focus Group. Counting on such a solid and varied base was a key pulling factor to expand the network and become interesting to many new stakeholders

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[CENTRINNO Focus Group Workshop Series](#)

The CENTRINNO Focus Group Workshop Series engaged external experts interested in familiarising with the project approaches and the uptake of project results. The five workshops focused on the project key concepts: Heritage, Social Inclusion, Circularity, Vocational Training, Fab City Hubs. Each event displayed CENTRINNO approaches, the methods, and the tools applied to the five themes, showcasing concrete pilot experiences through local partners' voices. Presenters, local actors and external experts engaged in panel debates, collaborative sessions and discussions on each of the themes proposed.

The goals of the CENTRINNO Focus Group were on the one hand to share with external stakeholders the results of research and implementation activities. On the other hand, the Focus Group aimed at making available the results and experiences so as to inspire the adoption of new approaches to similar urban and social development opportunities. The workshops favoured interesting exchanges around possible replication paths, adaptations or alternative ways, thereby starting reflections on the mainstreaming of project practices, and the routes for policy upscale and transfer.

The CENTRINNO Focus Group was also seen as a base room to explore potential thematic synergies and install new networks of soft cooperation and partnerships.

Results achieved:

The Focus Group engaged with more than 50 external experts from Europe and beyond. Such a wide pool of experts enabled critical exchanges around cutting edge topics of urban development and social innovation, thereby unlocking potential opportunities for policy transfer.

CENTRINNO FOCUS GROUP

Workshops Thematic Focus:

- 📅 Heritage
- 👥 Social inclusion
- ♻️ Circularity
- ✍️ Vocational Training
- 🌐 Fab City Hubs

HUB-IN ATLAS

[All Pilots & Alliance Cities / HUB-IN]

Main Objectives

- Provide a publicly accessible library of the current state of heritage led regeneration of Historic Urbana Areas in Europe
- Showcase how innovation and entrepreneurship can be stimulated and utilised in Historic Urban Areas.

Solution

A web database that provides an accessible overview of innovative and/or entrepreneurial initiatives that utilise heritage for the regeneration of urban areas.

Actors Involved

HUB-IN Partners

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

Ensuring HUB-IN Atlas Viability:

- Continuous Maintenance: Vital for sustained interest and knowledge sharing.
- Strategic Expansion: HUB-IN project uses the Atlas to support and advance HUB-IN Alliance cities.

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[HUB-IN Atlas](#)

The HUB-IN Atlas offers an interactive platform showcasing European heritage-led urban regeneration initiatives. Accessible via the website link, this tool presents a curated selection of cases, emphasizing 'good practices' rather than 'best practices' to acknowledge the context-driven nature of heritage-led projects. Among the criteria for case selection, geographic distribution across Europe and city sizes were considered. The Atlas currently features cases from 18 countries, encompassing cities of varied dimensions, ensuring comprehensive representation. With an evolving collection of 85 cases, the Atlas enables users to explore via an interactive map or filter menu. Each case profile highlights heritage use, initiative goals, stakeholders, and governance/financial structure. The Atlas also delves into data collection methodology, the HUB-IN Ecosystem approach, and FAQs. Focusing on innovations in governance, finance, and business models, the Atlas promotes inspiration for those embarking on heritage-led regeneration. The ongoing engagement with stakeholders is expected to expand and diversify the Atlas content, ensuring its continued value as a source of inspiration and guidance in the dynamic realm of European heritage-led urban regeneration.

Results achieved:

The HUB-IN Atlas compiles historic European cases of innovation, fostering knowledge exchange among cities. It's a dynamic database inspiring business models and ecosystem insights, promoting wider participation and learning.

Discover how historic urban areas can be regenerated through entrepreneurship and innovation.

RECOMMENDATION #6

PROMOTE DISTRIBUTED OPPORTUNITIES OF LIFELONG LEARNING AND VOCATIONAL TRAINING ON INNOVATIVE SKILLS THAT ARE RELEVANT AND TRANSFERABLE TO A DIVERSITY OF CONTEXTS.

[Policy Area: Knowledge transfer and capacity building]

Urban regeneration processes call for a continuous learning path based on the communication, dissemination and diffusion of innovative knowledge, vocational training, and professionalisation, involving local stakeholders and administrators. The fast pace of urban innovation and the experimental nature of projects suggests a coordinated and harmonised action at European level to promote lifelong training and constantly updated capacity building programs on heritage preservation, social innovation, and entrepreneurship. Blending together and integrating knowledge and capacities from a variety of urban regeneration processes, would allow offering a skillset that is relevant and transferable to different cities and contexts. However, it is not sufficient to create a fully-fledged knowledge and training repository at European level as the delivery and transmission of skills to local actors is the crucial step to fuel sustainable innovation. To bridge this step, it is key to promote training programmes and promote the creation of novel knowledge across local community centres or easily accessible public spaces. Only through a wider accessibility of this international expertise, social innovation can be sparked, also fuelled by networks of pilot experimentations that transfer mutual experiences based on a common skillset.

BUILDING A CREATIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IN POBLENOU THROUGH THE CENTRINNO SCHOOL

[Barcelona Pilot / CENTRINNO]

Main Objectives

- Retention of existing creative urban environments
- Development of new creative urban environments

Solution

Fostering local innovation: by bridging vocational training and real-world challenges in Poblenou

Actors Involved

Educational Department of Catalonia (in charge for vocational training); Fab Lab Barcelona/ IAAC (intersection between technology and society); Vocational training school, professors and students; Local businesses (proposing challenges to students); BIT Habitat, the Urban Innovation Centre of Barcelona (providing access to space and infrastructure)

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- Including the methodology and activity in the student's school curriculum helps bringing them closer to a much more real working environment
- Combining the event with an existing educational programme allowed to scale up the methodology to the whole Catalonia region
- Keep track of the contact between students and the organization and provide the necessary support for the development of the solutions

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[CENTRINNO School](#)

The Barcelona CENTRINNO School works towards bridging the gap between vocational training and the world outside the classroom. The Barcelona pilot developed methodologies, educational programmes and events to connect local and global challenges, as well as communities' strengths, with formal vocational training programs. By fostering the potential for local innovation in the Poblenou neighbourhood, the pilot provided resources and the necessary support to inspire students for the design and development of solutions to face local challenges in a real environment.

The challenges were mapped and proposed by local organisations and companies in the Poblenou neighbourhood. These challenges were presented and distributed among different profiles of students, who had the opportunity to prototype initial ideas, following a design thinking methodology, and present it for a final selection of winners. The selected projects, after being approved by a jury, were announced and supported by Fab Lab Barcelona and CatalunyaFP for their implementation during the students' courses. In collaboration with each participating organization, the students had the opportunity to explore new strategies and ideas and develop products and services to be implemented.

Results achieved:

- A design thinking method developed, validated and shared in open platform for replicability (MOOC format)
- Participation of 1200 students and 60 VT centers, considering the 2 editions of the Hackathon
- Close collaboration with VT centres and teachers embed the methodology in the curricula adopted by VTs.

SPROUT TANK FOR A CIRCULAR & CLIMATE NEUTRAL COLINA DO CASTELO

[Lisbon Pilot / HUB-IN]

Main Objectives

- Interdisciplinary knowledge exchange and experimentation of solutions suitable for historic neighbourhoods.
- Promote circular economy and climate neutrality at a neighbourhood scale, while enhancing cultural and architectural heritage.

Solution

Combine heritage-driven innovation to tackle renewable energy barriers, short food cycles, and climate resilience, including a Knowledge Sharing Community fostering local dialogue and a Sprout Tank Experimental Program incubating circular economy ideas.

Actors Involved

Leaders: Municipality of Lisbon and Lisboa E-Nova
C40, Universities and Research Centres, Private Entities, NGOs, CSOs

Feasibility Conditions

Establish effective communication channels among stakeholders and garner their interest through engaging strategies. Establish funding mechanisms for experimentation. Curate a pool of compelling testable solutions. Streamline permit acquisition process for public space solutions.

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[HUB-IN Lisboa Action Plan](#)

HUB-IN Colina do Castelo in Lisbon employs heritage-driven innovation to tackle barriers in implementing renewable energy in historic buildings, promoting short food cycles, and enhancing climate resilience in public spaces. The initiative comprises two interconnected activities.

Climate Neutral Historical Neighbourhoods Knowledge Sharing Community: This community fosters networking activities rooted in Colina do Castelo, promoting dialogue among businesses, governmental/non-governmental entities. It sparks climate-focused initiatives and synergies with projects like Infrablue European Project, C40's "Students Reinventing Cities" challenge, and SOLIS platform. It's a resource hub supporting the Sprout Tank program, cultivating climate experts.

Sprout Tank Experimental Program: The "Sprout Tank" incubates climate-neutral, circular economy ideas in Colina do Castelo. By connecting intervention needs with innovative solutions, it transforms spaces for experimentation—public/private, streets, buildings—into hubs for technological and social innovation.

The Knowledge Sharing Community fuels the program by forming opportunity spaces, partnerships, and expert mentorships. It amplifies the opportunity space pool, attracting promoters/entities for sponsorship. HUB-IN Colina do Castelo blends heritage with innovation, empowering historic neighbourhoods to adopt renewables, local food production, and climate resilience. Expected outcomes encompass advancing renewable energy, fostering a sustainable community, enhancing climate adaptation, promoting circularity, preserving heritage, creating well-being spaces, exploring art-sustainability links, and strengthening local community bonds.

CIVIC CURRICULA

[Bilbao Pilot / T-Factor]

Main Objectives

- Leverage temporary uses as novel forms of learning and capacity-building in response to community issues
- Boost creative collaboration and co-creation between Universities and grassroots communities
- Enrich urban regeneration processes with bottom-up spatial experiments that help protect, preserve, and enhance local identity and sense of belonging.

Solution

Novel processes and pathways of higher education that leverage temporary uses to test and advance new forms of capacity-building and cross-sectoral collaboration in address to local challenges of urban regeneration.

Actors Involved

University of Deusto, Mondragon University, IED Kunsthal, Bilbao Ekintza, Espacio Open, Tecnalía, grassroots organisations, cultural and creative businesses, T-Factor international partners

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- Provision of a wide range of expertise and capacities at the international level, which helped the local partners in moving forward from early hypotheses to full experimentation
- Special effort invested in participatory design and trust creation from the early stages, in order to support shared agency and participatory decision-making
- Importance of flexibility and loose forms of capacity-building and knowledge creation vis-à-vis the rigidity that university curricula may have.

The T-Factor pilot in Zorrotzaurre (Bilbao) deliberately addressed temporary uses as a means to explore novel forms of learning and capacity-building rooted in co-creation and multi-stakeholder collaboration in response to local challenges of urban development. The pilot has run 3 thematic paths of co-creation respectively on the topics of climate resilience; circular and collaborative economy; sociality and wellbeing. These paths (or curricula) involved young university students throughout the design of temporary experiments that could demonstrate viable ways forward to place-based solutions, leveraging a wide range of expertise and knowledge from across local authorities, universities, grassroots organisations, cultural and creative businesses, and more.

Results achieved:

- More than 150 University students actively involved in the design and prototyping of spatial experiments in response to local challenges, improving or developing new knowledge and capacities for inclusive, sustainable, and vibrant placemaking
- Several prototypes were developed and tested, demonstrating possibilities for 'light' interventions on the urban hardware that also foster social outcomes and benefits.
- Opened opportunities for higher education innovation, thus shifting the experiment run by T-Factor to a more permanent path of higher education within University degrees and curricula.

RECOMMENDATION #7

CREATE A LONG-LASTING COMMUNITY AROUND THE LOCAL REGENERATION PROCESS BY OFFERING A PLATFORM (DIGITAL AND PHYSICAL) FOR DIFFERENT STAKEHOLDERS TO CO-DESIGN AND PARTICIPATE IN LOCAL DEVELOPMENT PROCESSES.

[Policy Area: Networks of innovation & communities of practice]

The urban innovation process, fuelled by knowledge and skills in continuous evolution, relies on networks and communities of practice. The creation, valorisation and tightening of such networks is important to provide fertile ecosystems for the sharing of knowledge, experiences and best practices. The local dimension of this collaboration is a key element in the consolidation of new capacities, developed in experimental projects, and especially in their adaptation to the needs of each local reality. A common set of capacities (see also recommendation #6) shall be integrated and infused with local specific knowledge and information to achieve impactful innovation. To achieve this blend, it is necessary to create and support a long-lasting community around the local regeneration process (that stays beyond a specific project lifetime). The long-term consolidation of local networks and communities of practice calls for the institution of a stable point of contact at the municipality, including a dedicated and accessible public space, for citizens and local actors to meet, exchange and co-design, thus fuelling the ecosystem creation. The space shall take the form of both physical and digital forums to achieve the widest social inclusivity (see also Recommendation #2).

MANIFATTURA MILANO PLATFORM

[Milan Pilot / CENTRINNO]

Main Objectives

- Showcase and promote community activities in craftsmanship and circular economy.
- Attract and support more local businesses interested in circular processes.
- Foster an ecosystem for sustainable urban transformation

Solution

Establishing a digital and physical community for local circular manufacturing in the city of Milan

Actors Involved

Owners: Municipality of Milan, Nema Network

Community members: Local businesses, academia, makers, designers, NGOs

Audience: Citizens

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- H2020 funds and networking with other cities were fundamental for initiating the project.
- Public-private partnership allowed influencing local policies while engaging with stakeholders.
- There is a great need for constant community management

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[CENTRINNO Cartography](#)

[CENTRINNO Living Archive](#)

Manifattura Milano is a platform dedicated to craftsmanship, urban manufacturing and the circular economy in the fashion and design sectors. It has been developed within the Milan CENTRINNO Pilot's to create an ecosystem that synergistically develops circular processes at the urban level.

Organisations interact through subscribing to the platform's newsletter, publishing their events on the website for promotion. All involved stakeholders are present in an interactive map. The digital interaction is completed by a physical presence of the community in different types of events. Co-design sessions, focus groups, residencies and more. The biggest event organised thanks to an open call is Milano Circolare, which reinforced the community attracting more local businesses interested in circular processes and gave it visibility and access to valuable resources with 3.000 visitors in 2 days. Manifattura Milano, has achieved significant milestones, including creating discussions and co-designing strategies to support local circular manufacturing. Additionally, the platform facilitates training and collective discussions around circularity at the neighbourhood level and contributes to prefiguring possible Fab City Hubs models based on local business' and artisans' needs. The platform is perceived as a public good and a tool enabling civic participation, aligning with CENTRINNO's ethos of putting citizens at the core of urban transformation.

Results achieved:

- more than 100 organisations in the community
- increased awareness on circular local manufacturing
- more political consent and integration of Centrinno activities in the overall strategy for Circular Economy.

CARAVANE CREATIVE LAB: AN ITINERANT HUB OF INNOVATION

[Grand Angouleme Pilot / HUB-IN]

Main Objectives

- To support local professionals in the development of innovative narrative projects
- To raise awareness among the public and decision-makers of heritage issues via these narrative projects.

Solution

The “Caravane Creative Lab” (CCL) is an itinerant innovation hub dedicated to the valorisation of heritage and the creation of narratives anchored in the local urban geography and in coherence with the contemporary issues linked to urban regeneration and the global ecological crisis.

Actors Involved

Coordination: Metropolitan Trails Agency; GrandAngoulême Intercommunality.

Participation in the walks, suggestion of new entrants: Cultural and Creative Industries, local associations, local scholars, artists

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- Ensure voluntary engagement despite unpaid time.
- Address partner time concerns with personalized benefits.
- Prioritize face-to-face interactions to highlight advantages and foster word-of-mouth communication.

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[HUB-IN Grand Angouleme Action Plan](#)

To overcome the lack of a common space between the partners of the territory, and in particular the CCIs, Grand Angouleme team envisaged the creation of the “Caravane Creative Lab”, an innovation hub dedicated to the valorisation of heritage and the creation of narratives anchored in the local urban geography and in coherence with the contemporary issues linked to urban regeneration, sustainability and HUB-IN's Project goals. The CCL is an innovation hub built as a project platform open to all actors from the CCIs as well as to all artistic collectives, cultural actors, local associations and finally to all citizens wishing to better understand their territory, its heritage, its historical and ecological issues and wishing to set up editorial, audio-visual or playful projects in phase with the territory and the times we live in. Instead of meeting in a building, the hub meets outside in the city. Instead of meeting statically, the hub will meet walking, on the move. These travelling meetings/workshops creates a unique working and meeting space that doesn't exist for the moment. The monthly group walk is a new ritual for the stakeholders, a new space to create links. These collective days of walking through the territory allow members to share a convivial moment to discover different types of heritage elements and to meet selected actors and places. The objective is multiple: to meet potential partners for productions, to better know and understand the history and identity of the territory.

Expected results:

Access to historical heritage data; valorisation and sharing of stories and popular heritage; better protection of green and blue heritage; better knowledge of the different forms of heritage.

RECOMMENDATION #8

PROVIDE CITIZENS, STAKEHOLDERS, AND DECISION-MAKERS WITH DIRECT ACCESS TO KNOWLEDGE, BEST-PRACTICES AND HANDS-ON DEMONSTRATORS BY ORGANISING OPEN WORKSHOPS, RESIDENCIES AND EVENTS WITH INTERNATIONAL/HIGH-LEVEL GUESTS, TO SHOWCASE MODEL EXPERIENCES AND SUCCESS STORIES.

[Policy Area: Advocacy, influence capacity & communication]

The consolidation of innovative urban regeneration processes also depends on the capacity to generate advocacy momentum and increase the influence capacity of stakeholders and local actors towards the wide public and policy arenas. Such key enabling factors call for initiatives aimed at improving local actors' agency and the recognition of their voices in the policy debate. The current advocacy and communication frameworks would need increased effectiveness in valorising local contributions, including the provision of tools and platforms to amplify local stakeholders' voices and match them with the relevant policy makers. Such tools can take the form of open workshops, residencies and events with international-level guests where exchange around hands-on experiences, success stories and model demonstrators is facilitated. The allocation of resources and targeted efforts to a wide engagement, communication and advocacy seem particularly relevant when considering the experimental nature of pilot projects, which does not guarantee a powerful stance to influence the debate per se.

DECISION-MAKERS WORKSHOP: "HOW TO BUILD AN INNOVATION HUB IN RURAL ICELAND"

[Blönduós Pilot / CENTRINNO]

Main Objectives

- Provide elected representatives and local decision makers with insights on our pilot and Textile Center activities
- Work with a design-thinking approach to illustrate challenges, assumptions and create innovative solutions and ensure long-term support for our fab city hub
- Enable international project partners and local politicians to meet and share perceptions and ideas on makerspaces and innovation hubs

Solution

Cross-cutting workshop for decision-makers using a design thinking approach

Actors Involved

Leader: ITC. Participants: CENTRINNO Partners, Elected representatives from the Municipality Government, the Association of Municipalities in Northwest Iceland and the Húnabyggð mayor.

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

Hosting the session within the context of the CENTRINNO Consortium Meeting helped us to get policy makers' attention, give weight to the event and ensure participation. The session also significantly contributed in improving decision-makers perceptions towards FabCityHubs and the Icelandic Textile Center

We designed this workshop with the above mentioned objectives in mind. Workshop participants met for an afternoon workshop session in Blönduós during the Centrinno distributed Consortium Meeting in October, 2022. We started the session with a short "getting to know each other" game, introduced the FabCityHub concept and Design Thinking approach, and then divided participants into 5 teams, each having a local decision maker in the group. Their task was to brainstorm and share perspectives and ideas using the key questions of design thinking: what, who, where and make a collage of their ideal FabCityHub = a Textile Center in Blönduós, Iceland. At the end of the 3-hour workshop, groups presented their different posters and we all discussed the outcomes together.

Results achieved:

New insights - changed misconceptions - new ideas. Interestingly - and unbeknownst to group members -, all of the posters included elements of what the Textile Center already is doing or activities that are already in place: Groups e.g. suggested we host an international residency program and offer workshops bridging the gap from handcrafts to digital textiles. Discussing this really helped illustrate the value of an innovation hub and the opportunity that lies within establishing makerspaces in a city neighbourhood or rural region. Comparing posters and explaining ongoing activities also drove home the point that the Textile Center is already so much more than what some decision makers had thought. This has been very helpful for moving forward and getting our local policy makers' attention and support, e.g. mentions on social media, in interviews, and invitations to meetings and policy making sessions.

INTEGRATED DIGITAL PLATFORM DEDICATED TO CULTURAL AND CREATIVE INDUSTRIES DISTRICT

[Nicosia Pilot / HUB-IN]

Main Objectives

- Raise awareness of the HUA of Nicosia, its history and cultural heritage among local and foreign visitors
- Create a tourist product and enhance related business opportunities
- Promote synergies between the stakeholders, provide visibility to the users.

Solution

A platform/website hosts updated info aiding the growth of CCIs and HUA entrepreneurs. Linked to Nicosia's HUB-IN GeoTool, it backs the "CCI Quarter" project, aligning with city goals for Integrated Development Strategy's business encouragement in the area.

Actors Involved

Working group: Municipality of Nicosia, CYENS Centre of Excellence, Nicosia Tourism Board, Cyprus Energy Agency. Other stakeholders: Gardens of the future, Museums and galleries, Local entrepreneurs

Feasibility Conditions

- Effective communication of benefits and opportunities to ensure active participation of CCIs and engagement of stakeholders with diverse tools and resources.
- Consistently update information across all available tools, maintaining their relevance and usefulness

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[HUB-IN Nicosia Action Plan](#)

Nicosia faces challenges due to an UN-controlled Buffer Zone. Despite regeneration efforts, historic structures languish, and the Historic Urban Area (HUA) has limited tourism. Nicosia Municipality prioritizes culture and creativity, fostering diversification, sustainability, and innovation within the HUA.

CYENS Centre of Excellence, supported by the Republic of Cyprus, creates a 3D virtual replica of Nicosia. The Integrated Digital platform uses the existing Digital Twin to:

- Raise Awareness: Amplify the HUA's profile.
- Storytelling: Chronicle creative narratives.
- Heritage Preservation: Facilitate access to history.
- Tourism Enhancement: Shape a distinctive tourist offering.
- Stakeholder Synergies: Foster collaboration.
- User Visibility: Deliver a comprehensive interface.

Aligned with the "Cultural and Creative Industries District," the platform integrates with the HUB-IN GeoTool. This aligns with policies, cementing Nicosia's reputation as a vibrant cultural destination.

Results achieved:

- Streamlined record-keeping, monitoring, and support for Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) by the Municipality.
- Strengthened engagement and city branding, fostering cross-sector collaboration and relations with CCIs.
- Improved economic activity within CCIs, fuelling growth and innovation.
- Formation of a dynamic network among CCIs and stakeholders, amplifying synergies and fostering matchmaking opportunities.

LANDSCAPE FESTIVAL AND GREEN WORKING GROUP

[Amsterdam Pilot / T-Factor]

Main Objectives

- Generate visibility & appreciation for site as green space
- Mobilise and give voice to local communities for green initiatives
- Package green interventions for approval owners

Solution

A festival that invites participants to perceive the city 'with other eyes', engaging with it not as a built, but as a living environment of many species.

Actors Involved

Green coalition - local green initiatives supporting programme & communication; local communities - co-developing interventions to their environment; artists - researching the area and developing artistic interventions.

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

Conditions: bundling of activities for approval (small initiatives were previously not approved); at least 6 months for community-oriented preparation and design; involvement of artists for narrative and vision.

Take-away: Greening should engage local communities from start to finish; combine practical advantages of greening with intrinsic motivation to contribute to and be in nature; hyper-local orientation of the festival both in communications and stakeholders; positive narrative based on urgency

The Amsterdam Pilot of T-Factor shifted from solo eco-city programs to a community-centered approach. Over months, they partnered with local students, residents, and artists to create the 'With other eyes' festival. Attracting 8,000 daily park visitors, it aimed to change how people see their environment. Workshops allowed the public to join in crafting green interventions alongside local communities, fostering new skills. During the summer, the festival slowed down, introducing a park walking route that showcased these interventions. The route opened on midsummer night with a festive event, where participants presented their work. This approach transformed perceptions of the regeneration area, emphasizing urban coexistence with diverse life forms, the importance of biodiversity, and the benefits of urban green spaces. Decision-makers increased their appreciation for greenery and biodiversity, leading to adjusted maintenance practices for green spaces.

Visitors and communities reported heightened awareness and engagement with green and biodiverse environments, creating a more sustainable and vibrant urban landscape.

Results achieved:

Seven interventions were realised, alongside 15 workshops, a walking route and green coalition of 6 local groups connected to various other initiatives. The Field Atlas, a 'digital green twin' of the area, was developed. The Festival made a unique contribution to raise visibility of green initiatives on site, and demonstrated several ways to foster awareness and knowledge about the relevance and value of nature and biodiversity for quality of living in cities.

RECOMMENDATION #9

ESTABLISH A COMMON YET ADAPTABLE FRAMEWORK FOR MONITORING AND EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP TO FOCUS ON THE QUALITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE TRANSFORMATION ACHIEVED, BEYOND PURELY QUANTITATIVE MEASUREMENTS AND KPIS.

[Policy Area: Impact assessment methods]

The opportunities for consolidation and upscaling of experimental project experiences also depend on the principles and methods used to evaluate the social impact and innovation they brought to urban regeneration processes. Impact assessments would need a more socially relevant methodology allowing to go beyond purely quantitative evaluations and measurements solely based on KPIs. The multifaceted outcomes of experimental projects in this field require the establishment of a common framework that captures impact at societal level. This involves adopting methods that acknowledge and value intangible outcomes, including emotional aspects (place attachment, liveability, sense of participation), that are better suited to estimate the valorisation of heritage and the benefits of the urban regeneration process for the local community. Project spill over to the community, new skills introduced and the activation of innovation seeds (not yet mature by the project end) should also be recognised and valued as part of a learning process that already returns the first impact goals

IMPACT ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK WITH OUTCOME MAPPING

[All Pilots / CENTRINNO]

Main Objectives

- Monitor and evaluate performance through capacity building and organisational learning.
- Effectuating a common narrative of change among diverse stakeholders.
- Developing organisational practices for continuous improvement and sustainability of results.

Solution

Understand monitoring and evaluation as a pathway for achieving meaningful outcomes, diverse relationships, and sustainable organisational practices.

Actors Involved

Monitoring and evaluation team: coordinates the design and facilitates the execution of the impact assessment framework. Pilot team: Participates in design and planning and coordinates monitoring and evaluation. Boundary partners: individuals, groups, and organisations with which the pilot team directly interacts and seeks to influence.

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

The approach requires a participatory design process, which can take time and resources. However, the process enhances the self-organising capacities of communities that can then take over the process.

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[CENTRINNO Impact Assessment Framework](#)

The CENTRINNO impact assessment framework focuses on the monitoring and evaluation of three continuous processes of change:

1. Outcomes (pilot-level): This level concerns the monitoring and evaluation of the achievement of outcomes, understood as changes in terms of behaviours, relationships, and actions of the people, groups, or organisations with which the pilots work directly and seek to influence (boundary partners). Each pilot team determines at the beginning of every sprint a number of outcome challenges, along with progress markers reflecting graduated descriptions of achievement of these outcome challenges.

2. Strategies (resources-level): This level is related to the processes of experimentation carried out by the three core CENTRINNO platforms, namely the Cartography, Living Archive, and Fab City Hub Toolkit. The evaluation reflects the effectiveness of the platforms' tools and methods in enabling the achievement of pilot outcomes, while building the necessary organisational capacities to maintain and improve these outcomes.

3. Organisational practices (project-level): This level focuses on the monitoring and evaluation of the project's performance in implementing the CENTRINNO approach with the pilot cities. This is done through the documentation and assessment of patterns of organising that enable the transformation of city districts into Fab City Hubs. This level offers insights on the potential of maintaining and further advancing the project's outcomes and the systemic impact this may entail.

CENTRINNO impact assessment focuses on processes of change that lead to the desired impact in the long-term.

COMMON IMPACT ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK

[All Pilots & Alliance Cities/ HUB-IN]

Main Objectives

- Impact Assessment: Evaluate innovation hub activities for intended and unintended outcomes in economic, environmental, social, and cultural aspects.
- Process Evaluation: Assess the efficiency of each hub's operation and extract lessons to improve co-creation, innovation, and entrepreneurship.

Solution

The CIA Framework assists HUB-IN cities in comprehending benefits from activities in Historic Urban Areas. It offers a comprehensive framework to capture impacts, including economic, environmental, and social aspects. This approach, grounded in the theory of change, acknowledges the systemic nature of interventions and their long-term impacts

Actors Involved

HUB-IN Cities and their partners

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

Understand and document HUB-IN's benefits in Historic Urban Areas. Define suitable measures for economic, environmental, social impacts. Tailor to HUB-IN goals, adaptable to diverse contexts. Develop indicators using established methods, considering limits. Extract lessons for success replication.

Relevant Project Methods & Tools

[HUB-IN Common Impact Assessment Framework](#)

The HUB-IN Impact Assessment Framework aids HUB-IN cities in understanding and capturing benefits from activities in Historic Urban Areas. Designed to be comprehensive yet adaptable, it incorporates relevant metrics to gauge expected economic, environmental, and social impacts. While tailored to HUB-IN's goals, it remains flexible across technologies and local contexts. Drawing on established methods, it proposes indicators considering spatial, temporal boundaries, and effects like benefits displacement. The framework facilitates learning from pilot cities, amplifying successes to other historic cities. Its core aims are twofold: 1. Impact Evaluation: Assessing HUB-IN cities's contributions across economic, environmental, social, and cultural dimensions, whether positive or negative, intended or not. 2. Process Evaluation: Gauging Hub operations and extracting insights for co-creation, innovation, entrepreneurship. City-specific interventions yield bespoke indicators, while overarching impacts include reversing heritage neglect and fostering cross-sector collaboration. HUB-IN City Roadmaps and HUB-IN Action Plans define interventions based on challenges, aligning with Clusters, Ingredients, and Arrangements. The framework ensures a holistic view of HUB-IN's impact in each city.

THEORY OF CHANGE-BASED MONITORING & EVALUATION SYSTEM

[All Pilots / T-Factor]

Main Objectives

- Creation of the Theory of Change (ToC) and how change/impact can be understood and perceived, and adaptation as an operational framework suitable to the local context of the pilot cities
- Implementation and execution of a monitoring and evaluation process (M&E) of the ToC.

Solution

Effective Project Monitoring and Evaluation in T-Factor: Leveraging Narrative Theory of Change and Outcome Mapping for Improved Local Implementation.

Actors Involved

The M&E team has directly worked with actors (i.e. the persons executing the temporary uses) in order to create tools, including private organisations, NGOs, universities, etc. We've come indirectly in contact (through the actors) with the beneficiaries, including vulnerable groups, residents, community, private organisations, etc.

Feasibility Conditions & Lessons Learnt

- Finding a sustainable balance in its resources (time and money) for the pilot cities and M&E team
- M&E needs to be recognised as a tool to steer the strategy of the activity plan of the pilot cities, rather than being perceived as a bottleneck
- M&E is a learning process for the pilot cities and the M&E Team - several practices have been adapted throughout the process after the mid-term impact report

T-Factor is a very complex project with many different partners involved. For this reason we have created a narrative Theory of Change, which is more appealing and easier to understand when practitioners are less acquainted with the Theory of Change method. To apply the ToC to the local context of the pilot city, the project used the outcome mapping methodology. It is used for planning, monitoring, and evaluating development initiatives that helps a project team be specific about the beneficiaries it intends to target, the changes it hopes to see and the strategies appropriate to achieve these.

T-Factor created a M&E process in which specific M&E tools were crafted (i.e. interview questions, focus group material, surveys, and an observation template) together with the pilot cities. The project provided 1-to-1 guidance in the M&E process of the different pilot cities. It steered the pilots to better refine existing plans and intentions, and to enhance synergies and reinforcing loops between missions, activities, outcomes and impact. Finally, it constantly evaluates if the set of activities planned and executed, responds to the outcome indicators and targets the pilot city has set.

The practice supported T-Factor pilots in building up a complex ToC-based qualitative evaluation method that has been steered continuously in the last two years. In the last part of the project, a great emphasis has been set on the legacy component of T-Factor at the different pilot cities levels.

**TOWARDS INNOVATIVE,
INCLUSIVE AND CREATIVE HUBS
IN EUROPEAN CITIES**
POLICY REPORT

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